

SYNTHESES IN THE ACRIDINE SERIES. PART IV. N-SUBSTITUTED 2-METHOXY-7-CHLORO-9-AMINOACRIDINES

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2-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-aminoacridine and a number of its 9-substituted derivatives have been prepared, the substituents being aliphatic, aromatic and heterocyclic amino groups.

Browning and co-workers, who made an extensive study on the antiseptic action of acridine dyes (*Brit. Med. J.*, 1917, 73) introduced proflavine (3 : 6-diaminoacridine sulphate) and acriflavine (proflavine methochloride). Later on they synthesised similar compounds in pyridine, quinoline hydroquinoline and naphthoquinoline series (*J. Path. Bact.*, 1924, 27, 121; *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1922, B, 93, 329), but none of these compounds was as effective as the acridine compounds. It was thus concluded that the antiseptic properties of proflavine and acriflavine were really due to the acridine nucleus.

Recently Albert and Linnell (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1614; 1938, 22) and Albert, Rubbo and Goldacre (*Nature*, 1941, 147, 332, 709) have investigated the chemotherapeutic properties of a large number of mono and diaminoacridines and have shown that the simple aminoacridines, especially the 9-aminoacridines, are highly antiseptic. It has also been shown that introduction of chlorine atom into the acridine nucleus increases the bacterostatic properties; 3-chloro-9-aminoacridine is twice as active as 3 : 6-diaminoacridine, though it has the disadvantage of being more toxic. Introduction of alkoxy group also seems favourable from the point of view of antiseptic properties. Shaw (*Amer. J. Hyg.*, 1928, 8, 583) has shown that such groups increase the permeability of the drugs which affect the pharmacological properties favourably. Thus rivanol (2-ethoxy-6 : 9-diaminoacridine) is a better antiseptic than the parent 6 : 9-diaminoacridine.

Langer (*Z. ges. exp. Med.*, 1922, 28, 45) has established that with the increase in the molecular weight of acridine derivatives, the antiseptic action also improves and this is independent of chemical structure. Keeping these points in view, we have prepared 2-methoxy-7-chloro-9-aminoacridine and a number of its 9-substituted derivatives. These substituents include simple aromatic, aliphatic and heterocyclic amino groups. Because of the well known antiseptic action associated with sulphonamides, arsenicals and quinoline derivatives, a number of compounds have been prepared which comprise either of these groupings combined with the acridine nucleus.

4-Chloro-4'-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid (obtained by the condensation of 2 : 5-dichlorobenzoic acid and *p*-anisidine) and 4-methoxy-4'-chlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid (obtained by the condensation of 2-bromo-5-methoxybenzoic acid and *p*-chloroaniline) on treatment with excess of phosphoryl chloride give the same 2-methoxy-7 : 9-dichloroacridine. This has been condensed with various amino compounds to give N-substituted 2-methoxy-7-chloro-9-aminoacridines listed in Table I.

TABLE I

2-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-aminoacridines

(All melting points are uncorrected)

9-Substituent.	Melting points		Formula.	% Nitrogen	
	Base.	Hydrochloride.		Found.	Calc.
1. Amino	241°	312°(d)	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Cl	10.63	10.83
2. Phenylamino	204-05°	307-08°(d)	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ ON ₂ Cl, HCl	7.75	7.55
3. 4-Methylphenylamino	205°	318-17°(d)	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ ON ₂ Cl, HCl	7.32	7.27
4. 4-Methoxyphenylamino	204-05°	308-09°(d)	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ Cl, HCl	7.08	6.98
5. 4-Ethoxyphenylamino	172-78°	312-13°(d)	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ Cl, HCl	6.97	6.74
6. 4-Nitrophenylamino	210°	308°(d)	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₃ Cl, HCl	10.23	10.09
7. 4-Chlorophenylamino	193.94°	315°(d)	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ ON ₂ Cl ₂ , HCl	6.70	6.91
8. 4-Bromophenylamino	208°	312°(d)	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ ON ₂ ClBr, HCl	6.80	6.20
9. 4-Iodophenylamino	203-04°	277°(d)	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ ON ₂ Cl I, HCl	5.77	5.63
10. 2' : 6' Dichlorophenylamino	154-55°	244-45°(d)	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ ON ₂ Cl ₂	6.81	6.03
11. 4'-Acetylamino-phenylamino	247°	326-27°(d)	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ Cl, HCl	10.10	9.81
12. β-Naphthylamino	172-73°	303-04°(d)	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ ON ₂ Cl, HCl	6.74	6.65
13. cyclo Hexylamino	—	272-73°(d)	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ ON ₂ Cl, HCl	7.70	7.42
14. Phenylhydrazino	285°(d)	—	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ ON ₂ Cl	11.82	12.02
15. 4'-Carboxyphenylamino	276°(d)	—	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	7.20	7.37
16. 4'-Araeno-phenylamino	218-20°(d)	—	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ ClAs	5.79	6.10
17. Carboxymethylamino	231°(d)	—	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	8.60	8.84
18. Carboethoxyamino	169-71°	—	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	8.39	8.47
19. 2'-Dimethylamino-phenylamino	160-51°	242°	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ ON ₂ Cl, HC	10.98	10.14
20. 4'-Dimethylamino phenylamino	215-16°	291-92°	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ ON ₂ Cl, HCl	10.19	10.14
21. 4'-Diethylamino-phenylamino	208-07°	286°(d)	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ ON ₂ Cl	10.22	10.35
22. Piperidino	162°	—	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ ON ₂ Cl	8.42	8.67
23. 4'-Sulphanilamino-phenylamino	274-76°	—	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ ClS	10.07	10.16
24. 5'-Quinolinoamino	232-34°	—	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ ON ₂ Cl	10.68	10.89
25. 6'-Quinolinoamino	182-83°	—	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ ON ₂ Cl	10.56	10.69
26. Phenylazo-phenylamino	305-06°	—	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ ON ₂ Cl	12.80	12.77
27. β-Hydroxyethylamino	164°	—	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	9.00	9.26
28. β-Chloroethylamino	—	270-71°(d)	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ ON ₂ Cl ₂ , HCl	7.72	7.83
29. 4'-Acetylamino-phenylsulphonylamino	316-17°	—	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₂ ClS	9.0	9.28
30. 4'-Aminophenylsulphonylamino	—	Above 310°(decomp)	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ Cl S, HCl	9.15	9.38

(d) denotes decomposition

Compounds Nos. 2—21, 23—25 were prepared according to General procedure (I), while Nos. 22 and 27 were prepared according to procedure (II). In case of compound No. 26, amyl alcohol was used as the solvent, as in presence of phenol much colouring and tarry matters were obtained. In compound 22, the reaction was carried out in a sealed tube. Compounds Nos. 15, 16 and 17 were purified by precipitation with dilute acetic acid of their soluble sodium salts. 2-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(β -chloroethyl)aminoacridine (No. 28) was easily obtained by the treatment of the corresponding β -hydroxyethylaminoacridine with thionyl chloride. 2-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(p' -acetylamino phenylsulphonyl)aminoacridine (No. 29) was derived by the condensation of 2-methoxy-7-chloro-9-aminoacridine with p -acetylamino phenylsulphonyl chloride. This was hydrolysed to the corresponding p' -amino phenylsulphonylaminoacridine.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

4-Chloro-4'-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid was prepared according to Feldmann and Kopelivitch (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1935, 273, 488) by the condensation of 2 : 5-dichlorobenzoic acid and p -anisidine in 60% yield, though the above authors claimed a yield of 80%. A higher yield (75%) was obtained when potassium salt of 2 : 5-dichlorobenzoic acid was refluxed with p -anisidine and *iso*amyl alcohol in presence of a little precipitated copper and cuprous chloride. The reaction mixture was worked in the customary way. It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in greenish yellow needles, m. p. 189-90°. (lit. m. p. 185-86°) The same acid was also prepared by Margaret and co-workers through the Chappman synthesis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1955), m. p. 191-92°.

4-Chloro-4'-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxyl chloride was prepared by refluxing a suspension of the above acid in absolute petroleum ether with PCl_5 (1 : 1 mol. ratio) until a clear solution was obtained. It was recrystallised from petroleum ether in long, orange-yellow needles, m. p. 104°. (Found : N, 4.53. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_3\text{NCl}$ requires N, 4.73 per cent).

4-Methoxy-4'-chlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid was obtained by condensing 2-bromo-5-methoxybenzoic acid with p -chloroaniline according to the method already described (Singh and Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 224).

It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 197-98°, yield 73%. (Found : N, 4.91. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3\text{NCl}$ requires N, 5.04 per cent). The corresponding acid chloride was obtained in the usual way and crystallised from petroleum ether in deep yellow needles, m. p. 118°. (Found : N, 4.60. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_3\text{NCl}$ requires N, 4.73 per cent).

2-Methoxy-7 : 9-dichloroacridine.—Either of the above diphenylamine carboxylic acid (5 g.) was refluxed with phosphoryl chloride (40 c. c) for 4 hours. Excess of POCl_3 was removed under vacuum and the residue treated with ice-cold ammonia. The yellow product obtained after drying was crystallised from benzene in yellow needles. After recrystallisation from ethyl acetate, it melted at 212-13°. Drozdov (*J. Gen. Chem. U. S. S. R.*, 1935, 5, 690), who prepared it from 4-chloro-4'-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid, gives m. p. 205-06°. (Found : N, 5.18. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_9\text{ONCl}_2$ requires N, 5.03 per cent).

The compounds 2-17, 19-21, 21-25 (vide Table I) were prepared according to the general procedure (I).

Procedure (I).—2-Methoxy-7 : 9-dichloroacridine (1 g. 1 mol.) was dissolved in phenol (5 g.). The requisite amino compound (1.1 mol.) was added and the reaction mixture heated at 100° for 3 hours. After cooling, the reaction mixture was diluted with ether and the separated hydrochloride of the product was collected, washed with ether and chloroform. It usually crystallised from glacial acetic acid or absolute ethanol. The free base was obtained by decomposition of the hydrochloride with warm 5% sodium hydroxide solution. After drying it could be crystallised from a suitable solvent, usually alcohol.

The compounds Nos. 18, 22 and 27 were prepared according to procedure (II).

Procedure (II).—A mixture of 2-methoxy-7 : 9-dichloroacridine (1 g., 1 mol.) and phenol (5 g.) was heated on a steam-bath until a clear solution resulted. After this 1 mol. of the desired amine was added to the phenolic solution and heating continued for 3 hours. The cooled solution was poured into excess of 2*N*-sodium hydroxide, when a yellow coloured product separated. It was filtered and washed with water. The free base so obtained usually crystallised from dilute alcohol.

2-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(phenylazophenyl) aminoacridine (No. 26).—A mixture of the chloroacridine (0.5 g.), absolute amyl alcohol (8 c. c.) and *p*-amino-azobenzene (0.35 g) was heated at 110° for 3 hours when an orange coloured product separated. After cooling, petroleum ether was added and the orange product collected. It was thoroughly washed with ether and crystallised from glacial acetic acid in a voluminous orange pulp.

2-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(β-chloroethyl)aminoacridine (No. 28) was obtained by refluxing the corresponding hydroxyethylaminoacridine (3 g.) with thionyl chloride (12 c. c.) for 30 minutes. It was poured into excess of ice-cold water. After the decomposition of thionyl chloride, the yellow product was filtered and decomposed with 10% sodium hydroxide. The acridine base was extracted with chloroform. After drying over fused potassium carbonate it was precipitated by addition of alcoholic hydrogen chloride and recrystallised from absolute ethanol as orange needles.

2-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-aminoacridine was prepared by the treatment of the phenolic solution of 2-methoxy-7 : 9-dichloroacridine with ammonium carbonate in the usual way (*cf.* Singh and Singh, *loc. cit.*), yield quantitative. The base was crystallised from acetone in a yellow microcrystalline powder, m. p. 241°. It shows green fluorescence in chloroform, acetone and pyridine. The hydrochloride was crystallised from water as a yellow powder, m. p. 312° (decomp.) with previous darkening at about 280°.

2-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(*p*-acetylaminophenylsulphonyl)aminoacridine (No. 29) was obtained by the treatment of *p*-acetylaminobenzene sulphonyl chloride (1.3 mols.) with 2-methoxy-7-chloro-9-aminoacridine (1 mol.), dissolved in pyridine. The yellow powder that had separated after 24 hours was filtered and washed with absolute ether. It was recrystallised from pyridine as stout, yellow, glistening crystals. It shows a green fluorescence in pyridine.

2-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(*p*-aminophenylsulphonyl)aminoacridine (No. 30).—The above acetyl compound (0.5 g.) was heated with ethyl alcohol (74%, 25 c.c.), saturated with hydrochloric acid gas, in a sealed pyrex tube at 100° for 1 hour. After cooling, the yellow product that separated was collected and recrystallised from a large volume of absolute alcohol as a yellow powder.

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